

Etiologic Agents and Antifungal Susceptibility of Oral Candidosis from Romanian patients with HIV-infection or type 1 *diabetes mellitus*

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Abstract

This is the first Romanian investigation of oral candidosis in patients suffering of HIV-infection or type 1 *diabetes mellitus* (T1DM). *Candida albicans* was the dominant species in both types of isolates: n = 14 (46.7%) in T1DM, n = 60 (69.8%) in HIV. The most frequent non-*albicans Candida* spp. were *Candida kefyr* (n = 6; 20%) in T1DM and *Candida dubliniensis* (n = 8; 9.3%) in HIV. Resistance to fluconazole was detected only in the HIV non-*albicans Candida* group (n = 8; 9.3%). All isolates were susceptible to VOR. The experimental drug MXP had MIC values equal or close to the ones of VOR. Echinocandin resistance was more frequent than azole resistance.

Key words: antifungal susceptibility, MXP-4509, oral candidosis, Romanian HIV and diabetes patients

The presence of oral *Candida* yeasts is considered a biomarker indicative of immune system impairment and, in immunodeficiency disorders, can be correlated with a progressive disease (Vargas and Joly, 2002). Oral candidosis (OC) is the most frequent type of yeast infection and occurs especially in denture wearers and individuals with severe conditions, such as HIV-infected patients, those under antibiotic or chemotherapy, organ transplantation recipients and patients with systemic diseases such as diabetes (Vergani *et al.*, 2013).

HIV-infected patients are susceptible to opportunistic mycoses as cell-mediated immunity decays (Sangeorzan *et al.*, 1994). Before the era of highly active antiretroviral therapy (HAART), oropharyngeal candidosis (OPC) occurred in as many as 90% of patients, at some point during the course of HIV infection (Lortholary *et al.*, 2012). Since the initiation of HAART in 1996, there has been a decrease in the incidence of OPC (Leigh *et al.*, 2004) while oropharyngeal colonization varies from 44% to 62% (Lin *et al.*, 2013a).

To the best of our knowledge, the present study is the first Romanian investigation providing data regarding the etiologic spectrum and the antifungal susceptibility profile of OC isolates from patients with either HIV-infection or diabetes.

The 116 clinical yeast isolates included in this study were collected in three tertiary hospitals from different regions of Romania (*i.e.* Iasi, Timisoara and Brasov), from patients with overt OC. Of these patients, 30 were suffering from type 1 (insulin-dependent) *diabetes mellitus* (T1DM), while the other 86 were HIV infected (CD4+ T lymphocytes count < 500/mm³). The final identification was performed using ID32C strips (bioMérieux, France). Isolates identified as *Candida albicans* or *Candida dubliniensis* were further verified with duplex PCR (Romeo and Criseo, 2011). The isolates for which the ID32C strips gave inconclusive results were sent to the CBS-KNAW Fungal Biodiversity Centre, Utrecht (The Netherlands), where they were identified by MALDI-TOF MS or the sequence analyses of the ITS

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(Internal Transcribed Spacer) and the D1/D2 domains of the LSU (Large SubUnit) of the ribosomal DNA, as previously reported (Kolecka *et al.*, 2013).

In vitro susceptibility testing was performed following the EUCAST E. Def 7.1 guidelines (Subcommittee on Antifungal Susceptibility Testing (AFST) of the ESCMID European Committee for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST), 2008), for six antifungal agents: fluconazole (Sigma – St. Louis, USA), voriconazole (Pfizer Ltd. – Sandwich, UK), caspofungin (Merck & Co, Inc.), micafungin (Astellas Pharma, Japan), anidulafungin (Pfizer, Inc.) and the MXP-4509 experimental compound (“Petru Poni” Institute of Macromolecular Chemistry – Iasi, Romania), which is a triazole based nanoconjugate with β -cyclodextrin as a carrier molecule (Marangoci *et al.*, 2011). Two reference strains (*C. albicans* ATCC 90028 and *Candida krusei* ATCC 6258) were used for quality control. The interpretation of the MICs for the commercial antifungal agents was done according to the recent EUCAST document “Antifungal Agents. Breakpoint tables for interpretation of MICs”, version 7.0 (Subcommittee on Antifungal Susceptibility Testing (AFST) of the European Committee for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST), 2014).

Specific statistical parameters (Mode, MIC₅₀ and MFC₅₀ – for $n \geq 5$, MIC₉₀ and MFC₉₀ – for $n \geq 10$ and Geometric Mean – for $n \geq 2$, where n = the number of isolates) were calculated for each tested drug using Microsoft® Excel® (Dannaoui *et al.*, 2008). Statistical analysis was performed using a fully functional trial version of GraphPad Prism version 6.04 for Windows, GraphPad Software, La Jolla California USA, www.graphpad.com. Two-tailed *P*-values were calculated and $P < 0.05$ was considered significant. The level of significance was signalled in the text with one superscript asterisk (*) for $P \leq 0.05$ and two superscript asterisks (**) for $P \leq 0.01$. To calculate the geometric means and run the statistical tests, right censored values (MIC > the maximum tested concentration) were treated as the next theoretical value *i.e.* “> 8 mg/l” was treated as “16 mg/l” (Dannaoui *et al.*, 2008).

The overall species distribution and some of the calculated statistical parameters of the MICs are shown in Table I. Nine species were identified. In both types of chronic condition *Candida albicans* was the dominant species. Although it was surpassed by non-*albicans Candida* in the T1DM isolates, the statistical analysis revealed no significant differences in the distribution of species (*C. albicans* vs. non-*albicans Candida*) between the two categories. Cumulative antifungal susceptibility data (MIC₅₀, MIC₉₀, MFC₅₀, MFC₉₀) along with susceptibility and resistance rates for *C. albicans* and the non-*albicans Candida* group are presented in Table II. All the T1DM isolates and all *C. albicans* HIV isolates were susceptible to FLC. Based mostly on the 2 mg/l

non-specific BP for FLC, eight (30.77%) non-*albicans Candida* HIV isolates can be considered resistant, *i.e.* four *C. krusei* isolates, two of *Candida inconspicua* and two of *Candida norvegensis*. There was also two intermediately susceptible *Candida utilis* isolate. All isolates were susceptible to VOR. Two *C. albicans* and two *Candida tropicalis* T1DM isolates were resistant to all echinocandins, but they were susceptible to azoles. The *C. tropicalis* isolates also had high MFC values for CAS and ANI. There were also two *Candida lusitaniae* T1DM isolates resistant to CAS. Within the HIV isolates there were four of *C. albicans* that were resistant to MCA and ANI but were susceptible to azoles. All the non-*albicans Candida* HIV isolates were susceptible to echinocandins.

The antifungals MICs for the reference strains used for quality control were: *C. albicans* ATCC 90028 (0.125–0.25 mg/l for FLC, 0.0156 mg/l for VOR, 0.0156–0.0312 mg/l for MXP, 0.0625–0.125 mg/l for CAS, 0.0156–0.0312 for MCA, and 0.0156 mg/l for ANI); *C. krusei* ATCC 6258 (16–32 mg/l for FLC, 0.0625–0.125 mg/l for VOR, 0.0312–0.0625 mg/l for MXP, 0.0312–0.0625 mg/l for CAS, 0.0156–0.0312 for MCA, and 0.0312–0.0625 mg/l for ANI).

Articles regarding species distribution and antifungal susceptibility of oral isolates from patients with diabetes are relatively scarce and, unlike our study, they investigate isolates resulted from colonisation and not from OC. Even fewer go as far as testing antifungal susceptibility. Despite reports of increased presence of non-*albicans Candida* species, the most recent surveys from Brazil (Sanitá *et al.*, 2013; Bremenkamp *et al.*, 2011) or Western Europe (Manfredi *et al.*, 2002; 2006) document isolation rates of 70% and higher for *C. albicans*. The proportion in our study, approximately 50%, is more similar to reports from geographically closer areas such as Poland (Drozdowska and Drzewoski, 2008; Nawrot *et al.*, 2006), Slovakia (Dorko *et al.*, 2005) or Turkey (Kadir *et al.*, 2002). Regarding the non-*albicans* species, most studies report the isolation of *C. tropicalis*, but also *Candida glabrata* and *Candida parapsilosis*; the latter two did not occur in our investigation. The number of isolates and also the geographical gradient are important reasons for these differences. The Turkish survey reports *Candida kefyr*, while an older British survey reports *C. lusitaniae* (Manfredi *et al.*, 2002), species also reported by this study.

Our findings regarding FLC susceptibility are in agreement with the most recent Brazilian (Sanitá *et al.*, 2013) and British-Italian (Manfredi *et al.*, 2006) researches that found no FLC resistance. In contrast to the situation in Brazil, the Romanian isolates had a high rate of CAS resistance. Since there are no established BPs for CAS, we did use a non-specific BP of 0.25 mg/l which encompasses most of the already

Table I
Species distribution and *in vitro* antifungal susceptibility in oral candidosis isolates

Species (no. of isolates % of all isolates)	Compound	MIC ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)			MFC ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)		
		Range	Mode	GM ¹	Range	Mode	GM
T1DM isolates (n = 30) <i>C. albicans</i> (14–46.67%, 95% CI = 24.80–69.89%)	FLC	≤ 0.125 –0.25	≤ 0.125	0.1682			
	VOR	NA ¹	≤ 0.0156	0.1566			
	MXP	≤ 0.0156 –0.0625	≤ 0.0156	0.0210			
	CAS	0.0312–0.5	0.0312	0.0464	0.125–2.0	0.25	0.4529
	MCA	≤ 0.0156 –0.25	≤ 0.0156	0.0283	0.0625–2.0	0.125; 0.25	0.2500
	ANI	0.0312–0.25	0.0312	0.0420	0.125–1.0	0.125	0.2051
<i>C. kefyr</i> (6–20.00%)	FLC	0.25–0.5	0.25	0.3150			
	VOR	NA	≤ 0.0156	0.0156			
	MXP	≤ 0.0156 –0.0312	≤ 0.0156	0.0197			
	CAS	NA	0.0312	0.0312	0.0625–0.25	0.25	0.1575
	MCA	0.0312–0.0625	0.0625	0.0496	0.125–0.5	NA	0.2500
	ANI	0.0625–0.25	NA	0.1250	0.125–0.5	0.5	0.3150
<i>C. lusitanae</i> (6–20.00%)	FLC	≤ 0.125 –0.5	≤ 0.125	0.1984			
	VOR	NA	≤ 0.0156	0.0156			
	MXP	≤ 0.0156 –0.0312	≤ 0.0156	0.0197			
	CAS	0.0312–0.5	NA	0.1249	0.5–1.0	0.5	0.6300
	MCA	0.0312–0.25	NA	0.0787	0.125–0.5	0.5	0.3150
	ANI	0.0625–0.25	0.0625	0.0992	0.25–1.0	0.25	0.3969
<i>C. tropicalis</i> (4–13.33%)	FLC	≤ 0.125 –1.0	NA	0.3536			
	VOR	≤ 0.0156 –0.0312	NA	0.0221			
	MXP	≤ 0.0156 –0.0625	NA	0.0884			
	CAS	0.0312–1.0	NA	0.1766	0.25–16.0	NA	2.0000
	MCA	0.0625–1.0	NA	0.2500	0.25–1.0	NA	0.5000
	ANI	0.0625–2.0	NA	0.3536	1.0–8.0	NA	2.8284
Non-albicans <i>Candida</i> (16–53.33%, 95% CI = 30.11%–75.20%)	FLC	≤ 0.125 –1.0	≤ 0.125	0.2726			
	VOR	≤ 0.0156 –0.0312	≤ 0.0156	0.0170			
	MXP	≤ 0.0156 –0.0625	≤ 0.0156	0.0286			
	CAS	0.0312–1.0	0.0312	0.0810	0.0625–16.0	0.25	0.5000
	MCA	0.0312–1.0	0.0625	0.0884	0.125–1.0	0.5	0.3242
	ANI	0.0625–2.0	0.0625	0.1487	0.125–8.0	0.25; 0.5; 1.0	0.5946
Overall	FLC	≤ 0.125–1.0	≤ 0.125	0.2176			
	VOR	≤ 0.0156–0.0312	≤ 0.0156	0.0163			
	MXP	≤ 0.0156–0.0625	≤ 0.0156	0.0248			
	CAS	0.0312–1.0	0.0312	0.0624	0.0625–16.0	0.25	0.4774
	MCA	≤ 0.0156–1.0	≤ 0.0156; 0.0625	0.0519	0.0625–2.0	0.125; 0.25; 0.5	0.2872
	ANI	0.0312–2.0	0.0312	0.0824	0.0625–8.0	0.125	0.3618
HIV isolates (n = 86) <i>C. albicans</i> (60–69.77%, 95% CI = 54.80%–81.49%)	FLC	≤ 0.125 –0.5	0.5	0.2872			
	VOR	NA	≤ 0.0156	0.0156			
	MXP	NA	≤ 0.0156	0.0156			
	CAS	≤ 0.0156 –0.0312	0.0312	0.0291	0.0625–2.0	0.0625	0.1984
	MCA	≤ 0.0156 –0.0312	≤ 0.0156	0.0163	0.0312–2.0	0.0625	0.1575
	ANI	≤ 0.0156 –0.0625	0.0312	0.0312	0.0625–2.0	0.0625	0.1469
<i>C. dubliniensis</i> (8–9.30%)	FLC	0.25–0.5	0.25	0.2973			
	VOR	NA	≤ 0.0156	0.0156			
	MXP	NA	≤ 0.0156	0.0156			
	CAS	NA	0.0312	0.0312	0.5–1.0	1.0	0.8409
	MCA	0.0312–0.0625	0.0312; 0.0625	0.0442	1.0–4.0	1.0	1.4142
	ANI	0.0625–0.125	0.125	0.1051	0.125–1.0	0.5	0.4204
<i>C. kefyr</i> (4–4.65%)	FLC	NA	0.5	0.5000			
	VOR	NA	≤ 0.0156	0.0156			
	MXP	NA	≤ 0.0156	0.0156			
	CAS	NA	0.0312	0.0312	0.0312–0.0625	NA	0.0442
	MCA	NA	0.0625	0.0625	0.125–0.25	NA	0.1768
	ANI	NA	0.125	0.1250	0.25–0.5	NA	0.3536

Table I. Continued.

Species (no. of isolates % of all isolates)	Com- pound	MIC ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)			MFC ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)		
		Range	Mode	GM ¹	Range	Mode	GM
<i>C. krusei</i> (4–4.65%)	FLC	32.0–64.0	NA	45.2548			
	VOR	0.25–0.5	NA	0.3536			
	MXP	0.25–0.5	NA	0.3536			
	CAS	NA	0.125	0.1250	0.125–0.25	NA	0.1768
	MCA	0.0625–0.125	NA	0.0884	0.125–0.25	NA	0.1768
	ANI	NA	0.0625	0.0625	NA	0.125	0.1250
<i>C. tropicalis</i> (4–4.65%)	FLC	0.25–0.5	NA	0.3536			
	VOR	NA	0.0312	0.0312			
	MXP	0.0312–0.0625	NA	0.0442			
	CAS	NA	0.0312	0.0312	0.125–2.0	NA	0.5000
	MCA	NA	0.0312	0.0312	NA	1.0	1.0000
	ANI	NA	0.0625	0.0625	0.25–1.0	NA	0.5000
<i>C. inconspicua</i> (2–2.33%)	FLC	NA	32.0	32			
	VOR	NA	0.25	0.25			
	MXP	NA	0.125	0.125			
	CAS	NA	0.125	0.125	NA	0.125	NA
	MCA	NA	0.0312	0.0312	NA	0.0625	NA
	ANI	NA	0.0625	0.0625	NA	0.125	NA
<i>C. norvegensis</i> (2–2.33%)	FLC	NA	16.0	16			
	VOR	NA	0.0312	0.0312			
	MXP	NA	0.0312	0.0312			
	CAS	NA	0.0625	0.0625	NA	0.25	NA
	MCA	NA	0.0312	0.0312	NA	0.125	NA
	ANI	NA	0.0312	0.0312	NA	0.125	NA
<i>C. utilis</i> (2–2.33%)	FLC	NA	4.0	4			
	VOR	NA	0.125	0.125			
	MXP	NA	0.0625	0.0625			
	CAS	NA	0.0312	0.0312	NA	0.0312	NA
	MCA	NA	0.0312	0.0312	NA	0.0625	NA
	ANI	NA	0.0312	0.0312	NA	0.0312	NA
Non- <i>albicans</i> <i>Candida</i> (26–30.23%, 95% CI = 18.51%–45.20%)	FLC	0.25–64.0	0.25; 0.5	1.7044			
	VOR	≤ 0.0156 –0.5	≤ 0.0156	0.0430			
	MXP	≤ 0.0156 –0.5	≤ 0.0156	0.0408			
	CAS	0.0312–0.125	0.0312	0.0453	0.0312–2.0	0.125; 1.0	0.2370
	MCA	0.0312–0.125	0.0312	0.0453	0.0625–4.0	1.0	0.3631
	ANI	0.0312–0.125	0.0625	0.0733	0.0312–1.0	0.125	0.2370
Overall	FLC	≤ 0.125 –64.0	0.5	0.4920			
	VOR	≤ 0.0156 –0.5	≤ 0.0156	0.0212			
	MXP	≤ 0.0156 –0.5	≤ 0.0156	0.0209			
	CAS	≤ 0.0156 –0.125	0.0312	0.0333	0.0312–2.0	0.125	0.2094
	MCA	≤ 0.0156 –0.125	0.0156	0.0222	0.0312–4.0	0.0625	0.2027
	ANI	≤ 0.0156 –0.125	0.0312	0.0404	0.0312–2.0	0.125	0.1698

¹ GM–Geometric Mean; ² NA–Not Applicable

established echinocandin BPs. This situation requires further research, especially considering the findings of a recent study that echinocandins would be a safer choice for diabetes patients since they do not seem to be affected by glucose, which appears to significantly lower the antifungal activity of azoles and polyenes (Mandal *et al.*, 2014).

Studies that investigate isolates from HIV patients are more abundant, but similarly to those targeting dia-

betes, more of them focus on the asymptomatic carriage of yeasts in the oral cavities. Nevertheless, oral colonisation of HIV-infected patients in conjunction to low counts of CD4 cells are strong premises for subsequent development of OPC (Fong *et al.*, 1997). The same increase of prevalence for the non-*albicans* species is documented for HIV patients and, equally, *C. albicans* remains the dominant species. *C. dubliniensis*, *C. glabrata*, and *C. tropicalis* are considered as

Table II
Cumulative antifungal susceptibility data and resistance (R) rates of oral candidosis isolates

Species	T1DM				HIV				R (n-%)
	Compound	MIC ₅₀ (µg/ml)	MFC ₅₀ (µg/ml)	R (n-%)	MIC (µg/ml)		MFC (µg/ml)		
					MIC ₅₀	MIC ₉₀	MFC ₅₀	MFC ₉₀	
<i>Candida albicans</i>	FLC	≤0.125		0–0.0%	0.25	0.5			0–0.0%
	VOR	≤0.0156		0–0.0%	≤0.0156	≤0.0156			0–0.0%
	MXP	≤0.0156		NA	≤0.0156	≤0.0156			NA
	CAS	0.0312	0.25	2–14.3%	0.0312	0.0312	0.125	1.0	0–0.0%
	MCA	≤0.0156	0.25	4–28.6%	≤0.0156	≤0.0156	0.0625	2.0	4–6.7%
	ANI	0.0312	0.125	2–14.3%	0.0312	0.0312	0.125	0.5	4–6.7%
Non- <i>albicans</i> <i>Candida</i>	FLC	0.25		0–0.0%	0.5	32.0			8–30.8%
	VOR	≤0.0156		0–0.0%	0.0312	0.25			0–0.0%
	MXP	≤0.0156		NA	0.0312	0.25			NA
	CAS	0.0312	0.25	4–25.0%	0.0312	0.125	0.25	1.0	0–0.0%
	MCA	0.0625	0.25	2–12.5%	0.0312	0.0625	0.25	1.0	0–0.0%
	ANI	0.0625	0.5	2–12.5%	0.0625	0.125	0.25	1.0	0–0.0%
Overall	FLC	0.25		0–0.0%	0.5	4.0			8–9.3%
	VOR	≤0.0156		0–0.0%	≤0.0156	0.0312			0–0.0%
	MXP	≤0.0156		NA	≤0.0156	0.0625			NA
	CAS	0.0312	0.25	6–20.0%	0.0312	0.0312	0.125	1.0	0.0
	MCA	0.0625	0.25	6–20.0%	≤0.0156	0.0625	0.125	2.0	4–4.7%
	ANI	0.0625	0.25	4–13.3%	0.0312	0.125	0.125	0.5	4–4.7%

emerging pathogens (Lin *et al.*, 2013; Drozdowska and Drzewoski, 2008; Binolfi *et al.*, 2005).

Regarding *C. albicans* proportion within the HIV isolates, values similar to the one in this study (70%) have been reported for Taiwan (Ho *et al.*, 2014), Cameroun (dos Santos Abrantes *et al.*, 2014), USA (Merenstein *et al.*, 2013), Spain (Ramírez *et al.*, 2006) or Turkey (Erköse and Erturan, 2007). Percentages can go as high as 90% in India (Maurya *et al.*, 2013), Italy (Giammanco *et al.*, 2002) or UK (Cartledge *et al.*, 1999), 83% in South Africa (dos Santos Abrantes *et al.*, 2014), 79% in Serbia (Mitrovic *et al.*, 1996), or can go as low as 62% in Turkey (Erköse and Erturan, 2007) or Brazil (Costa *et al.*, 2006). Again, *C. glabrata* is missing from the isolates in our non-*albicans* *Candida* group.

Reported levels of FLC resistance vary widely from 0.9% in Taiwan (Ho *et al.*, 2014) and 3.4% in China (Li *et al.*, 2013) to about 50% in South Africa and Cameroun (dos Santos Abrantes *et al.*, 2014) for *C. albicans*. The differences can have a few possible causes such as street availability of antifungals, without prescription (dos Santos Abrantes *et al.*, 2014), or the different susceptibility testing methods used in each investigation. In our study, FLC resistance was present only in the non-*albicans* *Candida* group, in agreement with the above mentioned sources which found higher resistance rates for this group by up to 13% (Li *et al.*, 2013).

All the Romanian isolates were susceptible to VOR, a situation similar to that in Taiwan (Ho *et al.*, 2014).

Some resistance was found in China—3% for *C. albicans* and 14.5 % for non-*albicans* *Candida* (Li *et al.*, 2013) and very high values, were reported for *C. albicans* from South Africa and Cameroun (dos Santos Abrantes *et al.*, 2014). This study also signals the occurrence of resistance to echinocandins that other investigations did not report. Although these antifungals are not the first choice in treating patients with OC, they can be an effective alternative if topical or systemic azoles have definitely failed (Lortholary *et al.*, 2012).

Our study confirms a few worldwide reported tendencies such as the increasing prevalence and lower antifungal susceptibility of non-*albicans* *Candida* species, and *C. dubliniensis* as an emerging oral pathogen in HIV patients. It also supports the status of FLC as the first option for treatment, but not advisable for prophylaxis, and VOR as a viable second line of defence.

As a triazole based antifungal, MXP-4509 inhibits the ergosterol biosynthesis, similar to FLC and VOR. The experimental drug had a good antifungal activity with MIC values similar to those of VOR. Further, *in vivo* studies are warranted.

In conclusion, strict oral hygiene and adherence to specific treatment are the best prophylactic approaches to prevent OC in both chronic conditions, while FLC is recommended only as a first line of defense after the occurrence of the infection. As a second line of defense, in case of FLC therapeutic failure, echinocandins are a viable option for HIV patients. In the case

of diabetes patients, however, the risk of azole cross-resistance should be evaluated first; for patients without prior exposure to azoles, VOR may be a better option.

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